

Synthesis of substituted 3-chloro-1-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4*H*-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)-4-phenylazetidines

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Abstract : An efficient and extremely fast procedure to synthesize novel biologically active substituted trifluoro-2-azetidones heterocycles was discussed. Reaction of trifluoroacetic hydrazide **2** with hydrazine hydrate and then cyclization with tetramethoxy methane yields *N*-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4*H*-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)amine **3**. Condensation of the *N*-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4*H*-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)amine **3** with corresponding aldehydes yields Schiff base (**4a-k**). Reaction of Schiff base with chloroacetyl chloride yields the corresponding substituted 3-chloro-1-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4*H*-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)-4-phenylazetidines (**5a-k**).

Keywords : 2-Azetidones, Schiff base, triazoles.

Introduction

1,2,4-Triazole derivatives have been used as starting material for the synthesis of some important biologically active heterocycles. These compounds display diverse biological activity such as¹⁻⁶ anti parasitic, analgesic, antibacterial and anti-inflammatory. 2-Azetidones derivatives have been reported to possess anti-inflammatory⁷, anticonvulsant⁸, fungicidal⁹ and antibiotic¹⁰ activities. The incorporation of 2-azetidone moiety in *N*-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4*H*-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)amines has been found to enhance the activity. These observations promoted us to synthesize the title compounds (**5a-k**) as per the Scheme 1. Recently, Srivastava *et al.*^{11,12} have synthesized the substituted azetidines and reported their spectral and analytical data.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The reaction of hydrazine hydrate (90%) with trifluoroethyl acetate **1** yields the trifluoroacetic hydrazide **2** in quantitative yield as reported in literature¹³. Further trifluoroacetic hydrazide **2** reacts with tetramethoxy ethane and hydrazine hydrate (90%) to give the corresponding *N*-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4*H*-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)amine **3**. It was used as the starting material (main intermediate) to synthesize the title compounds **5a-k** in Scheme 1.

The condensation of the substituted aromatic aldehydes with *N*-amino triazoles **3** has been done to form corresponding Schiff bases **4a-k**. The reaction of Schiff bases with chloroacetyl chloride in acetonitrile yields the title compounds **5a-k**. The structural elucidation of the compounds **5a-k** has been discussed in the Tables 1 and 2.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. The ¹H NMR spectra were obtained on a Bruker 300 MHz spectrometer with CDCl₃ as the solvent. Tetramethylsilane (TMS) served as an internal reference and chemical shifts were expressed in δ (ppm). Mass spectra were recorded on a Finnigan-MAT GC-MS. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis. Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) was carried out in silica gel (MN-Kieselgel G, 0.2 mm thickness) and the plates were scanned under 254 nm ultraviolet light as well as the staining with iodine.

Synthesis of trifluoroacetic hydrazide **2** :

Trifluoroethylacetate (1.42 g, 0.01 mol) **1** and hydrazine hydrate (1.0 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (10 ml) were taken in a round bottom flask and the reaction mixture was heated at 70-75 °C for 4-6 h. After completion of the reaction (monitored through TLC), the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature. Solid was filtered and washed with 5 ml of ethanol. This material was dried under vacuum at 40 °C to obtain the 0.9 g of desired

Scheme 1

Table 1

Compd.	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	Found (Calcd.) (%)			Mass (M+1)
			C	H	N	
5a	72	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ClF ₃ N ₄ O ₂	45.04 (45.06)	2.91 (2.89)	16.16 (16.13)	345.04
5b	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ClF ₃ N ₄ O ₂	46.62 (46.65)	3.35 (3.32)	15.53 (15.50)	361.82
5c	75	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ClF ₃ N ₄ O ₂	46.61 (46.65)	3.33 (3.32)	15.52 (15.50)	361.79
5d	67	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ClF ₃ N ₄ O ₂	46.63 (46.65)	3.36 (3.32)	15.51 (15.50)	361.76
5e	78	C ₁₃ H ₉ Cl ₂ F ₃ N ₄ O ₂	40.90 (40.97)	2.35 (2.38)	14.65 (14.70)	382.16
5f	72	C ₁₃ H ₉ Cl ₂ F ₃ N ₄ O ₂	40.92 (40.97)	2.36 (2.38)	14.67 (14.70)	382.21
5g	70	C ₁₃ H ₉ Cl ₂ F ₃ N ₄ O ₂	40.91 (40.97)	2.34 (2.38)	14.68 (14.70)	382.20
5h	65	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ClF ₃ N ₄ O ₂	44.61 (44.64)	3.19 (3.21)	14.80 (14.87)	377.80
5i	67	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ClF ₃ N ₄ O ₂	44.62 (44.64)	3.20 (3.21)	14.79 (14.87)	377.78
5j	69	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ClF ₃ N ₄ O ₂	44.60 (44.64)	3.18 (3.21)	14.86 (14.87)	377.85
5k	62	C ₁₃ H ₉ ClF ₃ N ₅ O ₄	39.60 (39.86)	2.25 (2.32)	14.50 (14.55)	392.85

product. This material was used as such without any further purification. Yield 70%, m.p. 105 °C.

N-(3-(Trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)amine 3 :

The trifluoroacetohydrazide 2 (1.28 g, 0.01 mol) was taken in AcOH (10 ml) and cooled to 0 °C, tetramethoxy methane (2.04 g, 0.015 mol) was added to it slowly followed by hydrazine hydrate (0.75 g, 0.15 mol)

Table 2

Compd.	¹ H NMR data, δ CDCl ₃ , 300 MHz
5a	3.73 (3H, s), 5.20 (1H, d), 5.45 (1H, d), 7.18–7.25 (3H, m), 7.3–7.41 (2H, m)
5b	2.35 (3H, s), 3.71 (3H, s), 5.22 (1H, d), 5.44 (1H, d), 7.28–7.30 (4H, m)
5c	2.30 (3H, s), 3.76 (3H, s), 5.21 (1H, d), 5.40 (1H, d), 7.32–7.40 (4H, m)
5d	2.36 (3H, s), 3.71 (3H, s), 5.19 (1H, d), 5.35 (1H, d), 7.01 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz), 7.13 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz)
5e	3.70 (3H, s), 5.17 (1H, d), 5.35 (1H, d), 7.40–7.50 (4H, m)
5f	3.72 (3H, s), 5.19 (1H, d), 5.38 (1H, d), 7.38–7.40 (1H, dd), 7.56–7.60 (3H, m)
5g	3.65 (3H, s), 5.15 (1H, d), 5.38 (1H, d), 7.46–7.48 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz), 7.52–7.54 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz)
5h	3.75 (6H, s), 5.21 (1H, d), 5.40 (1H, d), 7.32–7.36 (4H, m)
5i	3.70 (6H, s), 5.19 (1H, d), 5.36 (1H, d), 7.40–7.42 (1H, dd), 7.52–7.54 (3H, m)
5j	3.67 (6H, s), 5.15 (1H, d), 5.37 (1H, d), 7.36–7.38 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz), 7.46–7.48 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz)
5k	3.69 (3H, s), 5.16 (1H, d), 5.39 (1H, d), 7.84–7.86 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz), 8.04–8.06 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz)

at this temperature and the reaction mixture was then heated at 90–95 °C for 24 h. After completion of the reaction (monitored through TLC), the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and then concentrated. The solid was taken in 100 ml of water, basified by saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and extracted with ethyl acetate (50 ml \times 3 times). Organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The purification was done on neutral alumina by using 70% of ethyl acetate/hexane as eluent to provide the title compound 3 (1.2 g, yield 67%). ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ 6.5 (2H, bs), 3.70 (3H, s); MS ES+ 183.15 (Found : C, 26.34; H, 2.67; N, 30.70. Calcd. for C₄H₅F₃N₄O : C, 26.38; H, 2.77; N, 30.77%), m.p. 126 °C.

General procedure for the synthesis of substituted *N*-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)(phenyl)methanimine (4a-k) :

A mixture of *N*-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)amine 3 (0.01 mol) and the correspond-

ing substituted aldehydes (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 mL) was treated with concentrated HCl (0.5 mL) and refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture on cooling was filtered and purified by recrystallization from ethanol to give 4a-k.

Synthesis of *N*-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)(phenyl)methanimine 4a :

Prepared from benzaldehyde, yield 80%, m.p. 158 °C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ 3.73 (3H, s), 5.60 (1H, s), 7.18–7.25 (3H, m), 7.30–7.42 (2H, m); MS ES+ 271.09 (Found : C, 48.90; H, 3.71; N, 20.70. Calcd. for C₁₁H₉F₃N₄O : C, 48.89; H, 3.36; N, 20.73%).

Synthesis of *N*-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)(*o*-tolyl)methanimine 4b :

Prepared from *o*-tolualdehyde, yield 76%, m.p. 162 °C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ 3.70 (3H, s), 2.7 (3H, s), 5.62 (1H, s), 7.28–7.32 (4H, m); MS ES+ 285.1 (Found : C, 50.80; H, 3.86; N, 20.03. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₁F₃N₄O : C, 50.71; H, 3.90; N, 19.71%).

Synthesis of *N*-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)(*m*-tolyl)methanimine 4c :

Prepared from *m*-tolualdehyde, yield 79%, m.p. 160 °C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ 3.68 (3H, s), 2.6 (3H, s), 5.8 (1H, s), 7.58–7.60 (4H, m); MS ES+ 285.1 (Found : C, 50.80; H, 3.86; N, 20.03. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₁F₃N₄O : C, 50.71; H, 3.90; N, 19.71%).

Synthesis of *N*-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)(*p*-tolyl)methanimine 4d :

Prepared from *p*-tolualdehyde, yield 84%, m.p. 165 °C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ 3.68 (3H, s), 2.4 (3H, s), 5.8 (1H, s), 7.24–7.26 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz), 7.58–7.60 (2H, d); MS ES+ 285.1 (Found : C, 50.80; H, 3.86; N, 20.03. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₁F₃N₄O : C, 50.71; H, 3.90; N, 19.71%).

Synthesis of (2-chlorophenyl)-*N*-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)methanimine 4e :

Prepared from *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde, yield 78%, m.p. 172 °C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ 3.72 (3H, s), 6.2 (1H, s), 7.58–7.60 (4H, m); MS ES+ 305.7 (Found : C, 43.80; H, 2.62; N, 18.73. Calcd. for C₁₁H₈ClF₃N₄O : C, 43.37; H, 2.65; N, 18.70%).

Synthesis of (3-chlorophenyl)-*N*-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)methanimine 4f :

Prepared from *m*-chlorobenzaldehyde, yield 82%, m.p.

170 °C. ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ 3.68 (3H, s), 6.4 (1H, s), 7.58–7.60 (4H, m); MS ES+ 305.1 (Found : C, 43.80; H, 2.62; N, 18.73. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{ClF}_3\text{N}_4\text{O}$: C, 43.37; H, 2.65; N, 18.70%).

Synthesis of (3-chlorophenyl)-N-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)methanimine 4g :

Prepared from *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde, yield 85%, m.p. 175 °C. ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ 3.70 (3H, s), 6.4 (1H, s), 7.58–7.60 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz), 7.26–7.28 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz); MS ES+ 305.1 (Found : C, 43.80; H, 2.62; N, 18.73. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{ClF}_3\text{N}_4\text{O}$: C, 43.37; H, 2.65; N, 18.70%).

Synthesis of N-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)(2-methoxyphenyl)methanimine 4h :

Prepared from *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde, yield 82%, m.p. 168 °C. ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ 3.40 (3H, s), 3.62 (3H, s), 5.8 (1H, s), 7.64 (4H, m); MS ES+ 301.6 (Found : C, 48.80; H, 3.62; N, 18.73. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{F}_3\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$: C, 48.00; H, 3.69; N, 18.66%).

Synthesis of N-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)(3-methoxyphenyl)methanimine 4i :

Prepared from *m*-methoxybenzaldehyde, yield 75%, m.p. 166 °C. ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ 3.70 (3H, s), 3.52 (3H, s), 6.1 (1H, s), 7.58–7.60 (4H, m); MS ES+ 301.4 (Found : C, 48.80; H, 3.62; N, 18.73. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{F}_3\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$: C, 48.00; H, 3.69; N, 18.66%).

Synthesis of N-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)(4-methoxyphenyl)methanimine 4j :

Prepared from *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde, yield 82%, m.p. 178 °C. ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ 3.70 (3H, s), 3.58 (3H, s), 6.2 (1H, s), 7.60–7.62 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz), 7.28–7.30 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz); MS ES+ 301.2 (Found : C, 48.80; H, 3.62; N, 18.73. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{F}_3\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$: C, 48.00; H, 3.69; N, 18.66%).

Synthesis of N-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)(4-nitrophenyl)methanimine 4k :

Prepared from *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, yield 80%, m.p. 180 °C. ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ 3.74 (3H, s), 6.3 (1H, s), 7.74–7.72 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz), 7.36–7.34 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz); MS ES+ 316.4 (Found : C, 42.00; H, 2.58; N, 23.01. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{F}_3\text{N}_5\text{O}_3$: C, 41.91; H, 2.56; N, 22.22%).

General procedure for the synthesis of substituted 3-chloro-1-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)-4-phenylazetidin-2-one (5a-k) :

A mixture of substituted *N*-(3-(trifluoromethyl)-5-methoxy-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)(phenyl)methanimine (4a-k) (0.01 mol) in acetonitrile (20 ml) was added (0.01 mol) to chloroacetyl chloride and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for overnight. After the completion of reaction, and monitoring it by TLC the reaction mixture was diluted with 50 ml of water and extracted with ethyl acetate (50 ml \times 3 times). The organic layer was dried on anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Purification was done on silica gel 60–120 mesh by using 50% ethyl acetate/hexane as eluent to provide the title compounds 5a-k.

Antimicrobial activity :

Compounds 5a-k were tested for their antimicrobial activities using two fungal species, namely *Aspergillus fumigatus* (AF) and *Candida albicans* (CA). Two bacteria species namely, *Escherichia coli* (EC) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (SA), were also used for antimicrobial screening. The organisms were tested against the activity of solutions of concentration of 5 mg/mL of each compound using an inhibition zone diameter in cm (IZD) as criterion for the antimicrobial activity. The fungicide Amphotericin and the bactericide Tetracycline were used as references to evaluate the potency of the tested compounds under the same conditions. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of selected examples of the synthesized compounds

Compd.	Inhibition Zone Diameter (IZD) (mm/mg compound tested)			
	EC	SA	CA	AF
Control	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
5a	11	11	0.0	0.0
	++	++		
5b	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
5c	11	11	0.0	0.0
	++	++		
5e	17	16	14	15
	++	++	++	++
5j	13	14	0.0	0.0
	++	++		
5k	14	15	0.0	0.0
	++	++		
Tetracycline	32	34		
	+++	+++	-	-
Amphotericin			20	16
	-	-	++	++

IZD = 2–10 mm beyond control = + (low activity)

IZD = 11–24 mm beyond control = ++ (moderate activity)

IZD = 25–35 mm beyond control = +++ (high activity)

The tests revealed that all compounds exhibited moderate activity against two bacterial species, except **5b** which showed no activity. All compounds exhibited almost no activity against *Aspergillus fumigatus* (AF), *Candida albicans* (CA) except compound **5e**, which showed moderate activity.

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References

1. A. A. Tayseer, A. D. Manal and M. H. Hamdi, *Molecules*, 2002, 7, 494.
2. A. Cansiz, M. Koparir and A. Demirdag, *Molecules*, 2004, 9, 204.
3. C. Katiea, D. Vesna, K. Vlado, G. M. Dora and B. Aleksundra, *Molecules*, 2001, 6, 815.
4. Z. Li-Xue, Z. An-Jian, C. Xian-Xin, L. Xin-Xiang, N. Xiangyun, C. Dong-Yung and Z. Zhang, *Molecules*, 2002, 7, 681.
5. T. R. Hovsepian, E. R. Dilanian, A. P. Engoyan and R. G. Melik Ohanjaian, *J. Chem. Het. Compds.*, 2004, 40, 1194.
6. A. A. F. Wasfy, *J. Chem. Res.*, 2003, 8, 457.
7. M. Muhammad and I. Bhat, *Indian J. Heterocy. Chem.*, 2003, 13, 183.
8. J. S. Birandar and Manjunath, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, 43, 141.
9. Pratibha Sharma and Ashok Kumar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, 43, 385.
10. J. M. Desai and R. Yadav, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2003, 42, 631.
11. S. D. Srivastava and R. Yadav, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, 43, 399.
12. S. D. Srivastava and S. K. Srivastava, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2008, 47, 606.

